

Cationic modulation of the proton's affinity for the membrane surface and the influence on the cellular energy machinery.

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Figure 1: TOC-graphic

Abstract

The cellular energy machinery crucially depends on the transmembrane proton potential difference (*protonmotive force*). Here we show that the presence of sodium ions at physiological salt concentrations reduces the proton's affinity for the membrane surface, and introduces a thermodynamic barrier between bulk and surface. In contrast, potassium ions have no effect. The different sodium concentrations within distinct cellular compartments lead to an asymmetric transmembrane proton free-energy profile. We discuss the effect this asymmetry might have on the *protonmotive force* at rest and under respiratory steady-state condition.

The proton concentration gradient between two cellular compartments is an essential part of the cellular energy machinery. In combination with the transmembrane electrical

potential difference ($\Delta\phi$), it generates a *protonmotive force* that is utilized to synthesize ATP [1]. Since measurements of the bulk-to-bulk *protonmotive force* correlate poorly with measured ATP yields [2, 3, 4], a simple equilibrium chemiosmotic theory is inadequate. Hence, a steady state model has been proposed (ref [5, 4] and references therein), in which the cell continuously pumps protons across the membrane. These protons are then retained at the surface, so that a sufficiently high *protonmotive force* arises between the two sides of the membrane.

On the surface, the proton, in the form of a hydronium, predominantly interacts with the lipid carbonyl and phosphor oxygens [6, 7], leading to a strong surface affinity [8, 9, 6, 7]. A similar strong interaction exists between Na^+ and lipid carbonyl oxygens [10, 11, 12, 13, 14], also accompanied by a strong surface affinity [15, 16, 17, 10, 13, 18, 19, 12, 11, 14, 20, 21, 22, 23]. In contrast, K^+ is mostly dissolved in the bulk [15, 18, 19, 14, 20, 21, 16, 24, 23]. This markedly distinct surface affinity of the two predominant cations in cells, Na^+ and K^+ , may affect the proton surface properties differently. Moreover, the non-uniform distribution of Na^+ and K^+ over varies cellular compartments [25, 26] may induce different proton surface properties on either side of the membrane involved in the energy machinery.

To investigate the effect of the cellular cation distribution on the proton membrane-surface affinity we have performed mesoscopic Monte Carlo sampling of ionic solutions in membrane separated compartments. To reach convergence, we treated the solvent and the membrane as a continuum. The ions were modeled as hard spheres with a radius equal to the hydration radius [27], and the ion-ion interactions were described by an effective Coulomb interaction [28]

$$V_{ion} = \begin{cases} \text{inf}, & r_{ij} < \sigma_{ij} \\ \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0\epsilon_{ij}} \frac{q_i q_j}{r_{ij}}, & r_{ij} \geq \sigma_{ij} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Figure 2: Ion-Membrane interaction potential normal to the membrane. The bilayer normal is set to zero at the Gibbs dividing surface.

where r_{ij} is the distance between ion i and j ; $\sigma_{ij} = (\sigma_i + \sigma_j)/2$ with σ_i and σ_j the hydration radius of ion i and j , respectively; and $\epsilon_{ij} = (\epsilon_i(z) + \epsilon_j(z))/2$ [29] with $\epsilon_i(z)$ and $\epsilon_j(z)$ the dielectric constant associated to the position normal to the membrane of ion i and j , respectively. The dielectric constant profile $\epsilon(z)$ changed smoothly from 78 in water to 4 in the membrane following the lipid tail density normal to the membrane. To account for the ion surface affinity, an effective ion-membrane interaction potential ($V_{mem}(z)$) was incorporated in our model. We used the free-energy profile of a single ion near a lipid bilayer as $V_{mem}(z)$ (figure 2), which was extracted directly from atomistic simulations of a single ion for the proton [7] and reverse engineered so that our model matched the ion density profiles observed in atomistic simulations for all other ions [10, 14, 19, 22, 16, 23]. The total potential energy of a system consisting of N ions, $V_{tot} = \sum_i \sum_{j>i} V_{ion} + \sum_i V_{mem}$, was used to accept or reject a new configuration according to a standard Metropolis criterium [30].

Because no accurate value for the sodium surface affinity has been determined [22, 31,

32, 21, 15, 14], we used a sodium membrane interaction potential (figure 2) that yielded sodium density profiles within the observed range, but considerably closer to the lower bound, as a conservative estimate.

The presence of other charged species in a cell membrane, such as proteins and anionic lipids, may also affect the proton surface affinity. Currently, we cannot model additional charges on the membrane because the corresponding single ion potentials of mean force are unknown. Nevertheless, the equal proton surface affinity for bilayers consisting of neutral or anionic lipids [8, 9] suggests a qualitatively similar cation effect in the presence of additional charges on the membranes.

We first assessed a single compartment with a proton in either a NaCl or a KCl solution at physiological concentration. The upper graphs in figure 3 show that the proton surface density in the KCl solution is significantly higher compared to the NaCl solution. Furthermore, in the NaCl system, both the H^+ and Na^+ density in proximity of the membrane surface displays a clear minimum, despite the absence of a barrier in the respective membrane interaction potentials (V_{mem}). This minimum was also seen in previous simulations of sodium salts in a membrane system [10, 13, 18, 19, 12, 11, 14, 23].

The lower graph of figure 3 shows that the presence of Na^+ significantly reduces the proton surface affinity. In contrast, no effect is seen in the presence of K^+ ions. The latter indicates that the proton surface affinity is not simply modulated by the ionic strength of the bulk solution. Rather, accumulation of cations on the membrane surface drives the change in the proton surface affinity.

The free-energy profiles in figure 3 also show that sodium at physiological concentration induces a thermodynamic barrier for the proton bulk-to-surface transition. A proton bulk-to-surface barrier has been observed in kinetic experiments [33], and it has been proposed that such an interfacial barrier can arise from a decrease in the water dielectric constant

Figure 3: Proton surface affinity in a NaCl or KCl solution. Proton free energy profiles normal to the membrane (lower graph) in a non-ionic (solid), 0.15 M NaCl (dashed) and 0.15 M KCl solution (dotted). The associated density profiles of all ions near a membrane in a 0.15 M NaCl (upper left) and 0.15 M KCl (upper right) solution are also given. The bilayer center is at zero in all graphs and color coding is proton (black), sodium (blue), potassium (cyan) and chloride (red).

near the membrane surface [5]. Our simulations show that the bulk-to-surface barrier can also arise due to accumulation of cations on the membrane surface.

The significantly different surface properties of protons in the presence of Na^+ or K^+ may influence proton/membrane experiments via the buffer solution. Both NaCl and KCl are commonly used as the basic salt in a buffer solution, but the influence of the cations on the results is often not discussed. For future experiments, we recommend careful consideration of the cations used in the buffer solution.

Figure 4: Modulation of the proton free-energy profiles normal to the membrane for physiological relevant NaCl concentrations.

To assess to what extent the proton surface affinity depends on the cation concentration for physiological relevant salt concentrations, we repeated the Monte Carlo sampling with salt concentration between 0.004 and 0.60 M. Figure 4 shows that, within this range, the proton surface affinity is reduced significantly for increasing NaCl concentrations, and a significant surface-to-bulk barrier appears. In contrast, the presence of KCl in the bulk solution does not affect the proton surface affinity at any of these concentrations. Note that at higher Na^+ concentrations, the surface ion density reached values at which three-body interactions start to become relevant ($> 0.5\text{M}$) [28], but this will only enhance the effect of the Na^+ surface competition with the proton, thereby decreasing the proton surface affinity even further.

To determine whether the concentration dependence is maintained in an asymmetric system that resembles cell conditions, we simulated two membrane-separated compartments at different ionic strength. The transmembrane proton free-energy profiles across the plasma and the mitochondrial inner membrane are depicted in figure 5 a and b, respec-

Figure 5: Free-energy profiles of a proton normal to a membrane that separates two cellular compartments, where (a) represent a plasma membrane and (b) a mitochondrial inner membrane. In grey, relevant free-energy differences are given.

tively. These graphs shows that the $[\text{Na}^+]$ gradient across the membrane creates a proton free energy difference between the two sides of the membrane. As a result, in an infinitely diluted system, pumping a proton from the inner to the outer membrane leaflet consumes free energy, which can be regained upon return of the proton to the inner membrane leaflet.

Since the cation density is significantly modulated near a membrane, the proximity of other membranes may further influence the cation surface properties, which is especially important for the proton circuit in the cristae of the mitochondrial inner membrane [34]. We have repeated the sampling of a two-compartment system that resembles a mitochondrial inner membrane, with the added complexity of a membrane shape that has similar dimensions as a cristae. These simulations revealed that the cation density profiles were virtually unaltered, demonstrating that the shape of the cristae does not alter cationic modulation of the proton distribution and associated free-energy differences.

The impact of the variation in the proton's surface affinity on the cellular energy machinery depends on the resulting *protonmotive force* (pmf)[35], $pmf = \Delta\psi - \Delta\mu_{H^+}/F$, with F Faraday's constant, $\Delta\psi$ the electrical potential difference and $\Delta\mu_{H^+}$ the proton

chemical-potential difference. The chemical-potential difference between positions r_i and r_j is $\Delta\mu_{H^+} = RT \ln(c(r_i)/c(r_j)) + \Delta G(r_i) - \Delta G(r_j)$, with c the concentration, ΔG the positional free-energy difference, which at neutral to high pH is given by our calculated free-energy profile, T the temperature and R the gas constant. At rest, only the membrane presents a large enough barrier to prevent equilibration of the chemical potential, and the resting *protonmotive force* is therefore unaffected by the specific proton surface affinity.

However, under respiratory steady-state conditions, the proton free-energy well at the surface allows, similar to a kinetic surface-bulk barrier [5], for an enhanced proton surface concentration on the outer membrane leaflet. The higher surface concentration leads to an increased transmembrane chemical-potential difference and an accompanying higher *protonmotive force*.

A consequence of the surface free-energy well is that the change in chemical-potential per translocated proton is more moderate than one would expect based on bulk-to-bulk measurements. As a result, more protons can participate in the energy machinery at a given steady-state chemical-potential difference than expected from a bulk-to-bulk analysis (for example before the proton pump feedback mechanisms are activated), which might promote proton pumping and lead to a higher overall ATP-production rate.

The increased proton participation does not explain the relevance of an asymmetric transmembrane proton free-energy profile. The possibility exists that the asymmetry is merely a side effect of Na^+ exclusion from the cell interior. In any case, a lower proton surface affinity on the outer membrane leaflet with respect to the inner leaflet yields a larger surface-to-surface chemical-potential difference per pumped proton, thereby increasing ATP yields.

In a broader context, we speculate that the sodium concentration may be actively used to manipulate the proton transmembrane chemical-potential difference, so that the

protonmotive force optimally matches the energetic requirements of the *protonmotive force* driven enzymes and the energetic losses may be reduced to a minimum. Especially when the proton translocation processes are already at their maximum rate, changing the sodium surface concentration may be useful to tune the *protonmotive force* to the enzyme's needs.

To summarize, we have shown that the proton affinity for the membrane surface is significantly modulated by the presence of sodium ions within physiologically relevant concentrations. In contrast, the potassium concentration has no effect on the proton surface affinity. Because the sodium concentration varies between different cellular compartments, an asymmetric proton free-energy profile exists across the separating membranes. At rest, the *protonmotive force* is not affected by the asymmetric free-energy profile. During respiration, however, the high proton surface affinity promotes proton pumping and the transmembrane asymmetry enlarges the change in chemical-potential difference per proton transition. Finally, we speculate that the sodium surface concentration could be actively changed to optimize the proton driven energy machinery.

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